

Deconstructing Decision-Making in the Analysis Phase of Latent Print Examinations

User Instructions for PiAnoS 4

PiAnoS Release 4.2.2-h0.2, <https://ips-labs.unil.ch/apps/pianos4-heidi/>

User Instructions Version 1.4.1 / HE / 22nd of February 2017

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	A word on the purpose of the study	3
2	Before beginning	4
2.1	Initial survey and informed consent	4
2.2	Compatibility check with your web browser	5
2.3	List of trials	5
3	The trial window in PiAnoS	6
4	Saving, Submitting, and Undo	8
5	Tools and Instructions	9
5.1	Quality tool (Q).....	9
5.1.1	<i>Your task with the Quality tool.....</i>	<i>11</i>
5.1.2	<i>A few tips to annotate quality.....</i>	<i>11</i>
5.2	Minutiae tool (M).....	13
5.2.1	<i>Your task with the Minutiae tool</i>	<i>14</i>
5.3	Ridge tracing tool (R)	15
5.4	Grouping tool (G).....	17
5.4.1	<i>Your task with the Grouping tool.....</i>	<i>19</i>
5.5	Other features annotation tool (O)	21
5.5.1	<i>Creases.....</i>	<i>22</i>
5.5.2	<i>Scars</i>	<i>23</i>
5.5.3	<i>Incipient ridges and dots</i>	<i>24</i>
5.5.4	<i>Pores.....</i>	<i>24</i>
5.6	Analysis questions, case notes, and conclusions.....	25
5.6.1	<i>Clarity</i>	<i>26</i>
5.6.2	<i>Distortion</i>	<i>26</i>
5.6.3	<i>General pattern</i>	<i>28</i>
5.6.4	<i>Level three detail.....</i>	<i>29</i>
5.6.5	<i>Case notes box.....</i>	<i>30</i>
5.6.6	<i>Suitability decisions.....</i>	<i>30</i>
6	Practice exercises	36
7	Thank you	36

1 Introduction

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study! This User Manual will walk you through the features of Version 4.2.2-h0.2 of PiAnoS, describe the tasks that are requested of you on each trial, and take you through two exercises to practice applying the instructions to fingermarks prior to embarking upon the experimental trials.

Regardless of whether you have participated in previous research studies using the PiAnoS interface, you are strongly requested to read this entire manual. PiAnoS has been updated for this study with new tools that were not previously available, and some aspects of the interface have also been modified from previous versions. Additionally, the way in which you were asked to use some tools in the past will differ in this study.

A tutorial video, which walks you through the use of the tools, may be optionally watched [here](#). A “Your Tasks” cheat sheet was also attached to your welcome email that summarizes *only* what you are being requested to do with each tool. The video will allow you to skip over the sections of the manual that explain how the tools work, but it is still strongly requested that you at least skim through the entire manual. It contains information that is not replicated in the video, and gives further explanation regarding how and when tools should be used and context for *why* many of the tasks are being asked of you. At a minimum, please either watch the tutorial *and* read the cheat sheet, or read the entire manual.

Previous research (both with and without PiAnoS) has revealed a high level of variability between examiners in annotation markups, but it is unknown how much of this variability is due to actual differences between examiner observations or training, and how much is due to differing interpretations of the instructions. In an attempt to reduce this second potential source of variability to the extent possible, you will be asked in Section 6 to complete two practice trials to check that you are following the instructions as intended. Please take these exercises seriously; they are the one chance you and the researchers have to resolve any miscommunications in how we would like the data to be collected prior to you beginning the experimental trials. You will receive feedback on your submitted responses to the two practice exercises before you begin the experimental trials.

1.1 A word on the purpose of the study

Each trial will ask you to provide a great deal of information about your analysis of the mark. Before you embark on this process, it may be useful to have a context – or some idea of *why* you are being asked to do these tasks.

The end goal of this research is to produce a standardized tool that can be used for measuring the utility (or usefulness) of a mark. In the context of this study, utility is considered to be multi-faceted. That is, it goes beyond simply value/no value and considers different applications for which it would be helpful to know the utility of the mark.

The study breaks this concept down into four suitability scales, which consider each mark in different ways. A brief 4-minute video describing why we have chosen to consider four aspects of mark utility is available [here](#). There are also links to short videos explaining each of the four scales below and in their respective manual sections.

The [first scale](#), the **value** scale, addresses the familiar question: is there enough here to proceed to a comparison?

The [second scale](#), the **complexity/QA** scale addresses the mark's potential for causing disagreements between examiners under the theory that the more complex a mark is, the more likely it is that two examiners will disagree on its suitability, sufficiency, or the interpretation of its features and distortion. The more complex a mark is, the more it should be subject to additional QA measures designed to reduce the risks of an error, or to create a transparent record of the interpretations that were made of the data.

The [third scale](#), the **AFIS** scale, addresses the familiar question: is this mark suitable for AFIS entry? But it also considers whether some marks, which bear additional risk for coincidental matches in a large database, should be subject to additional QA measures.

The [fourth and final scale](#), the **difficulty/training** scale, considers the difficulty level of the mark for research, training, testing, and testimony purposes. If marks could be sorted in a standardized way according to their difficulty, it would be possible to structure training programs and proficiency tests at known difficulty levels, which would be more helpful than a binary "competent/not competent" response.

In order to achieve this, the research is taking a hybrid examiner/algorithm approach. This is where the participants come in. We would like to better understand what information within a mark is the *most diagnostic* when making suitability decisions. To answer this question, we are using a white box approach to collect comprehensive data on what you consider when analyzing a mark.

Once we have this data, we will use machine learning to identify the most diagnostic information, which we will then combine with objective quality and rarity data to arrive at scores for each mark along each of the four scales.

Keep this information in mind as you work through the trials. While you are annotating the information you find useful in your decision-making process, be cognizant that at the end of each trial, you will be asked to render a decision along four suitability scales, not just one.

2 Before beginning

2.1 Initial survey and informed consent

Prior to signing in, you completed a welcome survey, the beginning of which is shown in Figure 1. This survey collected data on your demographics, experience, and agency policies, which will be used in aggregate to identify trends within the collective data. You also read an **informed consent form**, which detailed the risks and benefits of participating in the study, and is required to meet the standards of human subjects research.

Figure 1: Initial survey and informed consent

2.2 Compatibility check with your web browser

PiAnoS4 is coded in HTML5, SVG+Javascript. It requires no plugins to run. Normally all modern browsers can run PiAnoS4 smoothly (regardless of the operating system) using only stock browser functionalities. However, it may be incompatible with some old browsers (such as, for example, Internet Explorer 6, 7 or 8 under Windows XP).

2.3 List of trials

After signing in, you will see a screen listing the trials assigned to you (here reduced to the two you will complete to familiarize yourself with the instructions specific to this research, shown in Figure 2; you will have 30 trials to complete in the main body of the experiment):

Figure 2: List of trials that you are requested to complete. The logout link is at the top right of the page.

Select a trial by clicking on the associated link (for the purposes of this manual, the trial *User Manual Case* is used), then click on the “Start this exercise” button (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Once a trial is selected, click the “Start this exercise” button to initiate it.

3 The trial window in PiAnoS

A trial will appear in a window as shown in Figure 4. At any point, you can go back to the list of trials by clicking on PiAnoS 4.

Figure 4: User interface displayed at the start of a trial

The panels in PiAnoS 4.2.2-h0.2 are organized as follows (Figure 5):

Figure 5: Explanation of the panels in the PiAnoS user interface.

To move from one annotation tool to the other, and to activate/deactivate panels, the following keyboard shortcuts are available (Figure 6):

Keyboard Shortcuts	
Windows	
F	Toggle fullscreen mode
T	Toggle the toolbox (left pane)
C	Toggle the conclusion bar (bottom pane)
L	Toggle the layers and properties (right pane)
Tools	
E	Switch to the Edit tool
Q	Switch to the Quality tool
M	Switch to the Minutiae tool
O	Switch to the Other features tool
G	Switch to the Grouping tool

Figure 6: Shortcuts used to select annotation tools and activate panels

One advantage of the panel system is that panels can be hidden to focus your attention on the annotations. For example, in Figure 7, we show how the screen can be cleared (using

the F shortcut) of all side panels to concentrate only on the image to be assessed. All keyboard shortcuts remain active, allowing selection of the appropriate annotation tools, without having to activate the corresponding panel.

Figure 7: Use of the full screen mode (F). Each panel can be activated by using its shortcut: T, C, and L, or by clicking on its respective active middle segments. The shortcut F will activate/deactivate all panels at once.

4 Saving, Submitting, and Undo

Everything done in PiAnoS can be saved and undone or redone until submitted, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Saving, submitting, and undo/redo options

5 Tools and Instructions

During the analysis phase, the examiner gathers information about the mark in question until a decision is reached regarding the potential usefulness, or utility, of the mark for some practical application. It is the accumulation of information leading to this decision that interests us. **We wish to know, not the entirety of the information that may be visible, or inferable, in the mark, but what information was *diagnostic* for the examiner in reaching a suitability decision.**

The annotation tools available in this version of PiAnoS are designed to capture, to the extent possible, all the information the examiner considered and gave weight to during analysis of the mark. This section describes the functionality of each tool, and how you should use it to document your analysis of each mark.

5.1 Quality tool (Q)

Assignment of quality is made by delineating zones of perceived quality using the Quality tool (Q). PiAnoS 4.2.2-h0.2 uses the 6-level ANSI/NIST standard for extended feature documentation (Figure 9). **Use of the quality tool is not required.**

Figure 9: Selection of the Quality tool (Q) and options available for annotations

The Quality tool allows you to draw polygons delineating the corresponding level of quality. First click on a color patch to select the quality level desired. Then, one click on the desired region of the mark will start the first segment of the polygon, each additional click will begin a new segment of the polygon, and a double-click will close and finalize it.

The six levels are defined according to the ANSI/NIST standard as follows:

Quality tool

 Definitive Pores

 Definitive Ridge Edges

 Definitive Minutiae

 Debatable Minutiae

 Debatable Ridge Flow

 Background

main

Definition of the ANSI/NIST standard six-level system used in PiAnoS	
	An area is annotated in aqua if: <i>all detail</i> is definitive. Areas annotated in aqua are designated as having definitive pores .
	An area is annotated in blue if: <i>ridge flow, minutiae, and ridge edges</i> are definitive and unambiguous and pores are debatable. Areas annotated in blue are designated as having definitive ridge edges, debatable pores .
	An area is annotated in green if: <i>ridge flow and minutiae</i> are definitive and unambiguous and ridge edges are debatable. Areas annotated in green are designated as having definitive minutiae, debatable ridge edges .
	An area is annotated in yellow if: <i>ridge flow</i> is definitive and unambiguous and minutiae are debatable. Areas annotated in yellow are designated as having definitive ridge flow, debatable minutiae .
	An area is annotated in red if: ridge flow is debatable and no definitive minutiae are discernible, or are considered unreliable. Areas annotated in red are designated as having debatable ridge flow .
	An area is annotated in black if: no definitive or debatable ridge flow or minutiae are discernible, or are considered unreliable. Areas annotated in black are designated as background .

Notes and Definitions from ANSI/NIST:

Not Discernible or Unreliable: Features should not be marked and are ignored if present. No evidence for identification or exclusion in a comparison exists.

Debatable: Features may be marked, but presence, absence, and location are debatable. Corresponding or contradictory features on a comparison are supporting evidence for identification or exclusion.

Definitive and Unambiguous: Presence, absence, and location of features are definitive. Contradictory presence or absence of definitive features in a comparison to an image of equal or better quality is cause for exclusion.

If there is doubt as to which level of ridge quality to assign, use the lower quality.

5.1.1 Your task with the Quality tool

Use of the quality tool is not required in this study. However, if you choose to use the quality tool, please do so following these instructions. Using the chart in section 5.1 describing the six levels of quality, annotate the quality of the entire mark image, as shown in Figure 10. You do not need to black out areas outside of the mark image, but please *do* annotate areas that are part of the mark, but which you will ignore or not consider, using the red or black color, as appropriate. To clarify the ANSI/NIST instructions, **it is expected that there will be *no minutiae* marked in a red or black area.**

Figure 10: Quality annotations of the mark

5.1.2 A few tips to annotate quality

An annotated area can be selected (once the Edit tool is selected) by clicking on it. Multiple selection is possible using Ctrl-Click. Once selected, the anchor points used to construct the area are visible. Each of these points can be moved to reshape the polygon. The area and its anchor points can be further edited by using Ctrl-Click to open the drop down menu shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Further possibilities to edit quality zones using Ctrl-Click

Additional tips can be found in the help section of the Quality tool (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Help screen available for the Quality tool (Q)

5.2 Minutiae tool (M)

Minutiae are assigned as either ridge ending or bifurcation when their type and location are distinct and unambiguous on the mark. If you are certain a minutia is present, but the type is uncertain (i.e., a case of connective ambiguity), a specific annotation, called *Type unknown*, is used. However, if the location, or even the *existence* (and *de facto* type) of the minutia is uncertain, a fourth type of minutia, called *Uncertain minutia*, is used. Visual markers have been chosen to reflect the decreasing level of certainty. The four markers are shown in Figure 13:

Figure 13: Illustration of the four types of minutiae (in order from top to bottom)

To add a minutia, the process is very similar to how it is done on an AFIS system, as explained in the help screen of the tool (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Help screen available for the Minutiae tool (M)

Figure 15 shows the annotation of a minutia (a bifurcation) to a mark in analysis phase.

Figure 15: Left: Annotation of a minutia using the minutiae tool (M). Middle: Minutiae can then be selected (green outline), and moved by dragging within the green box. The annotation can be rotated by dragging the mouse outside the box. Right: To delete or edit the minutia type, use right-click. Note: Delete (←) will also delete the minutia when highlighted.

5.2.1 Your task with the Minutiae tool

Please mark all minutiae **that you considered** while making your suitability decision. For many marks, this will coincide with marking all minutiae you can find. However, not all minutiae are always part of the decision. For example, in a high quality image with many, many minutiae, you may reach a decision that the mark is suitable and unambiguous after 20 minutiae, and may not continue on to carefully examine all 40-80+ minutiae present in the image. If you find yourself thinking “I already have enough” after you have marked the first 20 minutiae (in this example), you should stop marking the minutiae at that point. On the other hand, in a low-quality mark, you may well need every feature you observe to reach your suitability threshold (whether personal or dictated by agency policy). In that case, you should be marking every minutia you find, because you are relying on all of them to support your decision.

Figure 16 illustrates a difficult mark with all minutiae annotated. To improve visibility of minutiae, the marker size can be adjusted (The example shows a marker size of 2; the default is 4). Keep in mind that for minutiae that are very close together (such as the two sides of an enclosure) you may need to use a small marker size to be able to mark both minutiae without accidentally grabbing the first minutia while trying to mark the second.

Again, as a matter of clarification from the ANSI/NIST instructions, **if you choose to annotate quality, it is expected that there will be no diamonds marked, except in a yellow area.** This is because a diamond indicates you are not certain of minutia location or existence, but green zones and higher indicate that minutiae are definitive and unambiguous. Thus, it would not be logically consistent to indicate you are uncertain where, or if, the minutia is (diamond) on an unambiguous minutia (green, blue, or aqua).

Similarly, **it is expected that there will be no triangles marked, except in a yellow or green area.** This is because a triangle indicates you are not certain of the minutia type, but blue and aqua zones indicate that edge shapes are definitive and unambiguous. Thus, it would not be logically consistent to indicate connective ambiguity (triangle) on a minutia that is so clear you can unambiguously see all the edges of the ridge (green or blue).

5.3 Ridge tracing tool (R)

It is useful to some to trace ridges (or alternatively, furrows) to help assess ridge flows. A specific tool has been designed to help in that task. **Ridge tracing is not required.** The tool can be used as deemed necessary by the examiner. Ridge tracings can also be made only in specific areas requiring assistance (typically when the quality is low). When the ridge tracing tool is activated (R), drawing the ridges is done by simply clicking along the ridge until a double-click finalizes the drawing (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Example of tracing a few ridges on the mark

All ridges can be edited and modified with the mouse (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Help screen available for the Ridge tracing tool (R)

When a ridge is selected, its anchor points can be moved, deleted (←) or modified (right click) as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Editing capability available for the ridges

5.4 Grouping tool (G)

The Grouping tool (G) is new to this version of PiAnoS. The Grouping tool can be used to group minutiae into a cluster. Once the tool is activated, each minutia that is clicked will be added to the cluster, until “Done” is selected at the top of the screen (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Click on a minutia to add it to a group. Click “Done” when all the minutiae that are part of your group are highlighted.

Sometimes several minutiae in proximity to one another will form a cluster that catches the examiner’s eye. If this cluster is near an anchor (such as a core, delta, or primary crease), it is often designated as a *target group* and used as a search image. If the cluster is not near an anchor, it still may stand out to the examiner and be given additional weight in their suitability decision due to a feeling that it imparts additional discriminability and/or searchability to the mark.

A sub-set of clusters is the *combined minutia* (Figure 21). The level two detail in a mark goes beyond just ridge endings and bifurcations; often these minutiae combine to make more complex combined minutiae (e.g., enclosures, hooks, crossovers, trifurcations).

Figure 21: Some examples of combined minutiae where two or more ridge endings or bifurcations combine to create a new formation.

For ease of reading, this manual will use the term *cluster* to refer to both combined minutiae and clusters of otherwise unrelated minutiae. It should also be noted that a cluster may include both one or more combined minutiae and other neighboring single minutiae (Figure 22).

Figure 22: An example of a cluster containing a combined minutia (bowtie, or opposed bifurcations) and a neighboring single minutia (bifurcation).

Once a cluster has been created, it will be added to a panel at the right side of the screen (Figure 23). Next to each cluster are two options that can be selected for that cluster: a flag and a trashcan. The flag icon will be described below. The trashcan icon is used to delete an entire cluster that you no longer want.

Clusters can be edited when the grouping tool is active by first selecting the cluster (Figure 23). This can be done either by clicking on any minutia within the cluster, or by selecting the cluster in the Groups panel. Once the cluster has been selected, all minutiae that are part of that cluster will be highlighted. To add a new minutia to the cluster, simply click on the additional minutia. To remove a minutia from the cluster, click on the minutia and it will be dropped from the cluster. If you make a change to a cluster, be sure to click “Done” at the end to save your changes to the cluster.

Figure 23: The Groups panel is located on the right side of the screen. It includes the trashcan icon, which can be used to delete a grouping. Clicking the name of a group will highlight all minutiae that are part of the group, and allow you to edit the group.

There is no limit to the number of clusters that can be created or how close minutiae need to be to one another to be part of the same cluster. However, a single minutia can only be part of one cluster; the same minutia cannot be assigned to more than one cluster at once.

5.4.1 Your task with the Grouping tool

It is not necessary to annotate every cluster of minutiae that you see. The goal of this research is not to test you on what you are able to find, but to understand what you find diagnostic about the information in a mark. Therefore, you should only group minutiae that are meaningful to you; if you see a cluster that you feel has extra weight (i.e., it adds more to your assignment of the value of the mark than an “average” minutia would, or you feel that if it was also present in the exemplar, it would carry a lot of weight with you), you should use the grouping tool to annotate it. If you notice a cluster, but you are unimpressed by it, you should not annotate it with the grouping tool.

It is not expected that any minutiae marked with diamonds will be part of clusters. By creating a cluster, you are indicating that you would give additional weight to this configuration of features, due to its increased selectivity or searchability; however, since a diamond minutiae indicates uncertainty about its location or existence, it would not be appropriate to assign it extra weight.

5.4.1.1 A point of clarification on when to use the Grouping Tool

Minutiae must be marked using the Minutiae tool (M) before they can be grouped using the Grouping tool (G). When you use the Minutiae tool, you are indicating that you have noted the minutia and it is counting toward your decision. This does not imply anything about whether you value it as a cluster; that is a separate decision. So, just because you decide *not* to make a single minutia part of a cluster, it does not mean that you should erase that minutia. The minutia may still have value singly, even though you are not assigning it

additional weight as part of a cluster. This is true *even if* the single minutia is part of a combined minutia that you are not choosing to annotate as such.

For example, you have marked the two opposing bifurcations that make up an enclosure using the Minutiae tool because you saw the enclosure and it is part of the minutiae that you are considering in your suitability decision. However, the enclosure is under the core of a whorl and you don't feel that it is particularly diagnostic – at least not more so than any other “average” minutiae. You decide *not* to use the Grouping tool to combine the two bifurcations into a cluster. You still leave the two individual bifurcations marked as minutiae that you are using (Figure 24).

Figure 24: A commonplace enclosure (lake) under the core of a whorl. In a situation like this, you may choose to mark the two bifurcations making up the enclosure, but not group them as a combined minutia because you are not giving the feature additional weight due to its low specificity.

5.4.1.2 Using the Target Group (flag) designation

You will click the flag icon next to any cluster that you choose to use as your initial target group (Figure 25). You may designate no more than one target group on a given mark.

Figure 25: The flag icon is clicked to change a combined group of minutiae into a Target Group.

Note that for purposes of this study, the function of a target group is *to help you search*. Therefore, a good target group must be located near an anchor (core, delta, primary crease, etc). A terrific cluster that is nowhere near a landmark that helps to locate it in space is less useful for searching; therefore, such a cluster can still be grouped, and thus given additional weight, but it is not a target group.

It is up to you *how* close a cluster needs to be to an anchor to make it a useful target group, but a good rule of thumb is 10 ridges or less. You may go farther away than 10 ridges if you wish, but you should feel that there is some connection between the target group and the anchor (i.e., that if the anchor was recorded on the corresponding exemplar, it is highly likely that the target group would also have been recorded; and that it should be easy to make your way from the anchor to the target group without intervening distortion or artifacts getting in the way).

If you would like to use a target group that you feel increases the searchability of the mark, but the target group is not very selective, you still may use the Grouping tool to create a cluster and designate it as a target group (this is an exception to the general rule that clusters should be highly selective). For example, you might choose to use a ridge ending a few ridges away from the core as a target group if you think it will help you search. A single ridge ending is not very selective, but if you are using it as your target, you should turn it into a group and flag it as your target group.

Finally, if you would like to designate a non-minutia feature (such as a scar) as your target group, you may use the case notes box (Section 5.6.5) to indicate this.

5.4.1.3 Designating highly diagnostic clusters

As was noted in section 5.4.1.1, there may be clusters that you do not choose to annotate as such because they do not stand out to you. Therefore, it can be inferred that if you *do* annotate a cluster using the Grouping tool, you are *de facto* indicating that it has stood out to you to some degree, and is above-average diagnostic in your eyes.

On occasion, you may notice a combined minutia or cluster of minutiae that *really* stands out to you. Examples of this would be the elusive trifurcation, or a small cluster of several unusual combined minutiae in close proximity. If you would like to indicate that you find this cluster to be *highly* discriminating, *highly* diagnostic, or just plain cool, you can use the case notes box (Section 5.6.5) to list the Combined Group number of the cluster and state that you found it to be extraordinarily diagnostic. This is your way of indicating that you think it is something really special, that it is contributing a great deal to your assignment of the value of the mark, or that you would give it a great deal of weight during a comparison. This is the sort of thing that, if you find it in the exemplar, you might say to yourself, “okay, I’m done; that’s all I needed to see”.

5.5 Other features annotation tool (O)

Other features such as scars, wrinkles or creases, incipients, pores, and dots can be indicated using a dedicated tool (O). As with the Minutiae and Grouping tools, **you should only annotate those other features that you are giving weight to, or considering in your decisions**. For example, if you can make out some faint pores, but you don’t intend to compare them, and they don’t add weight to your suitability decision, you should not

annotate them. Note that different marks have been used in this section to demonstrate the relevant features.

5.5.1 Creases

The crease tool allows you to create a polygon showing the shape of a crease or wrinkle. As with the quality tool, one click on the desired region of the mark will start the first segment of the polygon, each additional click will begin a new segment of the polygon, and a double-click will close and finalize it (Figure 26). Once the feature has been drawn, a right-click on the feature will open the editing menu (Figure 27).

An annotated area can be selected (once the **Edit tool** is activated) by clicking on it. Once selected, the anchor points used to construct the area are visible. Each of these points can be moved to reshape the polygon. Please note that the anchor points can only be dragged to reshape the polygon while using the Edit tool (the one that looks like an arrow). This will not work while the Other features tool is selected.

Figure 26: The crease tool allows you to draw the shape of any creases or wrinkles that contribute to your decision.

Figure 27: A right-click on the outline of the polygon will allow you add a point where you clicked, delete the point you clicked on, or delete the entire polygon. You can also activate the edit tool and select the polygon, then drag the anchor points to reshape it.

5.5.2 Scars

The scar tool allows you to create a polygon showing the shape of the scar (Figure 28). This polygon is created and edited the same way as was described for the crease tool (see Section 5.5.1).

Figure 28: The scar tool allows you to draw the shape of any scars that contribute to your decision

5.5.3 Incipient ridges and dots

The incipient tool allows you to draw a fine line indicating the axis and length of an incipient ridge. This tool can also be used to annotate dots that are too small to mark using the Minutiae tool. The incipient tool is used by clicking at one end of the feature, then double-clicking at the other end to finalize it. If the incipient ridge is long, or has curvature to it, you will click along its path, double-clicking at the end to finalize it (Figure 29).

Figure 29: The incipient tool allows for annotating incipient ridges and dots with a fine line

5.5.4 Pores

The pores tool is used to annotate any pores contributing to your decision. Once you have selected the pores tool, every time you click, a small green dot will appear (Figure 30). To delete a pore, right-click on it while the Other features tool is active.

Figure 30: The pores tool allows you to click on a pore to annotate it with a green dot

The possibilities for editing are very similar to the other tools. The help tips are as follows (Figure 31):

Figure 31: Help screen available for the Other features tool (O)

5.6 Analysis questions, case notes, and conclusions

The bottom panel of the interface poses several questions about observations you made during your analysis of the mark, and about your conclusions regarding the suitability of the mark along four different scales, which will be described below.

You are requested to complete your analysis and annotation of each mark prior to addressing the questions, or entering your suitability decisions.

You will be asked a series of questions to capture your observations in several areas of analysis, as well as your level of certainty in those observations and your perceptions of how much different aspects of the analysis contributed to your decisions. Each question will be dealt with separately below.

Please note that the size of the conclusions pane can be adjusted by grabbing the top of the pane and dragging.

5.6.1 Clarity

The Clarity question (Figure 32) aims to capture to what degree the clarity/quality of the image has impacted your decisions. Please select the option that best describes how you feel about the clarity of the mark. It is assumed that high clarity will influence you to want to keep the mark while poor clarity will influence you to want to discard the mark. **Note that your answer to the clarity question may not change whether you will keep or discard the mark, but only whether you want to keep or discard it.** For example, you may encounter a mark that has very low clarity, but has enough other useful information that it is still of value. In this case, the level of clarity increased your *desire* to discard the mark, but ultimately you did not discard it. It might be helpful to imagine a static threshold for suitability with a moving needle that indicates where you are at any moment in the decision process. If you are below the threshold before considering clarity, then clarity helps to move your needle toward suitability, you would choose “adds weight to my desire to keep the mark”, even if it doesn’t move your needle enough to cross the threshold.

Figure 32: The clarity question box

5.6.2 Distortion

As with level three detail, past research has shown that examiners vary greatly in their perception of distortion, their vocabulary to describe distortion, and their ability to diagnose the causes of observed distortion. Rather than trying to force participants to define the type of distortion they see, this study again concerns itself with the *effect* any distortion present has on the decision-making process.

Every impression contains *some* degree of distortion, since a 3-dimensional object is being impressed on a 2-dimensional surface. But for some impressions, this distortion is so subtle as to be negligible. For others, there is some noticeable distortion, but it does not impact interpretation of the information contained within the mark. At the other end of the scale, some images are severely distorted and, while information can be extracted from the image, a high level of interpretation and effort is required.

The Distortion question (Figure 33) aims to capture your perception of the level of interpretation and effort necessary to extract information from the mark.

Figure 33: The distortion question box

This question is meant to be interpreted globally – in other words, think of the overall effect of distortion on the entire mark. If the mark is generally clear, but there are some small areas that are impacted by distortion, or the entire mark is affected by some distortion, but it is minor and easy to explain with minimal interpretation, select “Low Distortion” (Figure 34). If parts of the mark are heavily distorted, but other areas of the mark are clear and the ratio is approximately equal, select “Medium Distortion” (Figure 35). If most of the image is impacted by heavy distortion, select “High Distortion” (Figure 36).

Figure 34: Examples of low distortion marks

Figure 35: Examples of medium distortion marks

Figure 36: Examples of high distortion marks

5.6.3 General pattern

In the general pattern question (Figure 37), you will indicate what pattern type you believe the mark to be. If you are certain of pattern type, select only one. If you are uncertain, you may select as many as you feel are possible. If you are unable to eliminate even one pattern type as a possibility, select unknown.

Figure 37: The general pattern question box allows you to indicate any pattern type(s) you believe the mark could be, or "Unknown" if you can't eliminate even one type. There is also an opportunity to indicate if something about the pattern shape stands out as highly distinctive (see below).

If you select multiple pattern types, please order them left to right from what you consider the most probable to the least probable. This can be done by dragging and dropping the pattern images. This ranking only needs to be done for the pattern types you select; unselected patterns can be ignored.

Please note that if you select unknown, you will be unable to additionally select any other pattern type because you have already indicated that you don't know with any certainty what type the image is or could be. Similarly, once you have selected a pattern type, you will

no longer be able to additionally select unknown as an option because you have indicated that you believe with some certainty that the image is, or could be, at least one pattern type.

If you select any pattern type (including unknown) in error, simply click it a second time to unselect it.

You will additionally be asked to answer a question below the pattern type images to indicate whether there is something distinctive about the pattern shape that makes it stand out. This goes toward the discriminability of the overall pattern, or ridge flow, and is independent of any particular minutiae. You will check this box if there is something interesting or unusual about the ridge flow, shape of the core, etc that really catches your eye and makes you think you would easily recognize it if you saw it again. An example of an unusual core shape is given in Figure 38. Another good example would be just about any of the “QUIP” marks that are featured at the back of each issue of the Journal of Forensic Identification.

Figure 38: A mark with an unusually shaped core that would make it stand out in one’s memory.

5.6.4 Level three detail

In the level three detail question (Figure 39), you will be given 3 choices to describe your perception of level three detail in the mark. Select the one that most closely matches your observations. Because different examiners define and use “level three detail” differently, we have purposely made no attempt here to dictate what you may consider as level three detail. However, as with the different types of level two detail that we already discussed with the introduction to the tools, we are interested in how much the perceived detail factors into your decisions.

Figure 39: The level three detail question allows you to indicate if you noted any level three detail at all, and if so, if you gave it weight

Therefore, you will notice that the concept of weight is integrated into the three options. If you don’t see any reliable level three detail, you will select “None noted”. However, if you

note reliable level three detail, you then need to consider whether you anticipate you would *use* that detail.

For example, most examiners agree that pores are a type of level three detail, yet few examiners actually compare pores. They may note that they are there, and they may use them as an indication of the quality of the image, but if they do not actually use them in a comparison, they should not be given weight during analysis since they will not contribute to the outcome of the comparison.

Under this example, if you noted pores, but you do not routinely compare pores, you would select “Some noted, but not given weight”. If you noted pores and you would compare them if pores were also present in the exemplar, you would select “Noted and given weight”. This same principle applies to anything you define as level three detail – if you see it *and you would use it*, select “Noted and given weight”. If you see it but would *not* use it, select “Some noted, but not given weight.”

5.6.5 Case notes box

A free text section is available (and can be easily resized in the interface). This area is intended to be used to capture any information you would like to share that wasn’t captured by one of the tools or questions. You may use it to capture written analysis notes, if that is your usual practice (but please note that typing written analysis notes does not replace using the annotation tools and questions! The text box is meant to be **optional** and supplemental).

Some examples of additional information you may wish to capture in the text box include:

- if you stopped annotating because you had “enough”, but want to acknowledge that there was other detail present that you saw and didn’t annotate
- if you answered “Noted and given weight” for the level three detail question and wish to share the type of level three detail you saw
- if you note a tonal reversal
- if you note a large open field that you wish to give weight to
- if you wish to single out a grouped cluster of minutiae as extraordinarily diagnostic
- anything else of note you wish to record

5.6.6 Suitability decisions

The suitability question will ask for your suitability decisions for the mark (Figure 40). While typically at this stage, a single response of value/no value is sought, in this study, we will be considering four separate scales of suitability, which will be examined here in detail. A video explaining why there are four separate scales can be found [here](#).

Figure 40: The suitability decisions box. You will be prompted to select a decision in each of the four tabs.

5.6.6.1 Value scale

The value scale considers whether the mark should be used in a comparison, and if so, how strong a conclusion it has the potential to reach. Rather than separating marks via Approach 1 or Approach 2, as previously described in the literature, this study considers that Value for Identification marks are not necessarily better than Value for Exclusion Only marks (they simply require different information), and that the distinction to be drawn should rather be between marks that contain sufficient information to cross *any* decision threshold versus those that may provide useful information, but do not rise to the threshold of an identification or exclusion conclusion. A video explaining this scale in more detail can be found [here](#).

Decision	Definition	Clarification
No value	The mark does not contain sufficient information to proceed with a comparison	This decision indicates that the mark does not contain enough information to be searched or compared at all, even to a single 10-print card; or if it was compared, it is not expected that the comparison would yield any useful information to inform an investigation or provide support for one source proposition over the other.
Some probative or investigative value, but insufficient for an	The mark contains sufficient information to proceed with a comparison, but insufficient	This decision indicates that the mark contains sufficient minutiae and orientation/location information that it

<p>identification or exclusion</p>	<p>information to reach either an identification or exclusion decision</p>	<p>could be effectively searched; however, the information is limited enough that if an association were made, it would not be strong enough to rule out the possibility that someone else could share the same features.</p> <p>Similarly, if the features in the mark were not found in an exemplar, or if apparent differences were found, they would not be sufficient to rule out the possibility that the mark <i>could have</i> been made by that source. This may occur, for instance, in marks with sufficient distortion that the features or anchors are somewhat unreliable.</p> <p>While there is not enough information to reach the highest level of reported conclusions, these marks still may be useful in providing investigative leads, or may provide support for one source proposition over the other.</p>
<p>Of value for a categorical conclusion*</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value for Exclusion only • Value for Identification only • Value for both Identification and Exclusion 	<p>The mark contains sufficient information to potentially reach either an identification or exclusion decision, or both</p>	<p>These decisions indicate that the mark is or may be identifiable or excludable.</p> <p>One conclusion is not considered to require better, or more, information than the other. If the mark is in this category, you will specify whether it is of value for an Exclusion only, an Identification only, or if it could be used for both an Identification and an Exclusion (assuming legible and completely recorded exemplars for each circumstance).</p>

* It is recognized that some laboratories *never* reach a categorical conclusion; that is, they report only on the strength of the association without taking the final step of declaring an identification. For those laboratories, the term Identification, as used here, will represent their strongest level of association.

5.6.6.2 Complexity/QA scale

The complexity scale considers the chance that two examiners will disagree about the suitability, sufficiency, or interpretation of features and distortion in the mark. The complexity scale aims to predict the marks that are prone to causing disagreements, which will in turn influence the quality assurance (QA) measures that will be appropriate for the mark. As marks become more complex, agency SOPs may dictate that they be subject to additional documentation requirements^a, additional verifications, blind verifications, or

^a We recognize that different agencies have different standards of documentation. For purposes of this study, “additional documentation requirements” presumes that standard documentation is fairly minimal. If an agency already does full documentation of every mark, they would not need to do MORE for complex marks, although they might to LESS for very

other quality measures. On the other hand, marks of very high quality may enjoy policies requiring minimal documentation and review. A video explaining this scale in more detail can be found [here](#).

Decision	Definition	Clarification
No value	The mark does not contain sufficient information to proceed with a comparison	This decision indicates that the mark does not contain enough information to be searched or compared at all; or if it was compared, it is not expected that the comparison would yield any useful information to inform an investigation or provide support for one source proposition over the other.
Of value, complex	The mark contains sufficient information to proceed with a comparison, but due to limitations of quality, a high degree of interpretation is required	<p>This decision indicates that the mark contains sufficient information to search and compare, but the high degree of interpretation required means that there is a high chance of variability in judgments between examiners.</p> <p>Disagreements may occur regarding suitability, sufficiency, or existence and type of features and distortion in this mark. The mark may be at or near the value/no value threshold.</p> <p>This mark should be subject to additional documentation and quality requirements. It is critical to thoroughly demonstrate the basis for any conclusions rendered on this mark.</p>
Of value, non-complex; requiring documentation	The mark contains sufficient information to proceed with a comparison, and while some interpretation may be required, no significant disagreements over suitability, sufficiency, or interpretation are anticipated	<p>This decision indicates that the mark contains sufficient information to search and compare, and the quality and quantity of information available is about average.</p> <p>This mark may require some interpretation, and there may be limited disagreements between examiners on suitability, sufficiency, or interpretation. This mark represents the average, run-of-the-mill mark encountered in casework.</p> <p>This mark should be subject to standard documentation and review requirements.</p>
Of value, non-complex; self-evident	The mark contains sufficient information to proceed with a comparison and requires minimal or no interpretation	This decision indicates that the mark contains sufficient information to search and compare, and that the overwhelming quality and quantity of information available makes the basis for any conclusions virtually self-evident. There should

high quality marks under this philosophy. Participants should assume that “requiring documentation” or “standard documentation” refers to a documentation requirement of, at a minimum, naming the mark, noting its type and orientation, and annotating some minutiae (e.g., those used to reach the suitability decision). “Reduced documentation” indicates only noting the name, type, and orientation of the mark. “Additional documentation” refers to fully documenting all information in the mark that has been used in analysis or comparison. Questions should be answered with these benchmarks in mind, considering what you think *should* be required, not necessarily what your agency *does* require.

		<p>be no expectation of disagreement between examiners regarding this mark.</p> <p>This mark can be subject to reduced documentation (e.g., only name the mark and indicate orientation and anatomical source) and review requirements.</p> <p>If this was a casework mark, you would feel that the documentation you have done to this point due to the requirements of the research was a waste of time (thank you for doing it anyway – we are going to use it!)</p>
--	--	---

5.6.6.3 AFIS scale

The AFIS scale considers whether a mark should be entered into an AFIS system, and if so, whether additional QA measures are warranted. In large databases, the chances of a coincidental match can be much greater than in comparisons to a known subject. Some qualities of a mark, such as low minutiae count, low specificity minutiae groupings, or high interpretation areas, can increase this risk. Additional QA measures can include ideas such as additional or blind verifications; using poor marks to generate investigative leads, but not to identify; or requiring that additional minutiae *not* entered in AFIS be found in agreement between mark and print before an identification may be declared. The QA measures to be implemented will be determined by agency policy, but this scale seeks to measure which marks you believe should be subject to *some* additional QA measure, whatever it may be^b. A video explaining this scale in more detail can be found [here](#).

Decision	Definition	Clarification
Not AFIS quality	The mark is not suitable for entry into an AFIS system	The mark may or may not be of value for comparison, but this decision indicates that it either does not meet your agency's threshold for AFIS entry, or if AFIS criteria are left to analyst discretion, you do not feel that the mark contains sufficient information for an effective AFIS search in your primary search system.
AFIS quality, with additional QA measures	The mark is suitable for entry into an AFIS system, but due to the presence of risk factors, additional QA measures should be used	This decision indicates that, while it meets your minimum agency or personal criteria for AFIS entry, this mark contains risk factors (e.g. low minutiae count, low specificity groupings, or high interpretation) for a coincidental match or contains unreliable information. You would

^b As with the documentation discussion, this question should be answered considering what you think *should* be required of all agencies, not necessarily to match what your agency *does* require.

		enter this mark into AFIS, but feel it would be prudent to apply additional QA measures as a precaution.
AFIS quality	The mark is unconditionally suitable for AFIS entry	This decision indicates that the mark meets or exceeds your agency or personal criteria for AFIS entry and does not contain risk factors or unreliable information. This mark is suitable for a standard AFIS entry procedure without need for additional caution beyond accounting for the size of the database in your decision-making process.

5.6.6.4 Difficulty/Training scale

The difficulty scale considers the difficulty level of the mark for training, testing, and testimony purposes and measures how difficult you anticipate it would be to compare the mark. We envision in the future that this scale will be a range between, for example, 1 and 10. Under such a scheme, a mark of difficulty 10 would equate to no value – that is, the mark would be so difficult to compare that you would not attempt it.

This scale can be used to assign difficulty levels to marks such that examiners can be trained to specific levels, tested at those levels, and ultimately testify at specific levels (i.e. by stating the difficulty level of a case image in relation to their tested proficiency level. This will provide jurors with a framework by which to judge how much weight to give the evidence). A video explaining this scale in more detail can be found [here](#).

For purposes of gathering data in this study, the difficulty scale will be resolved into three bins. This is because, for a human, the difference between a 6 and a 7 versus the difference between a 7 and an 8 is rather arbitrary, difficult to define, and time-consuming to determine. Thus, it will be much quicker and simpler to simply designate each mark as **low difficulty**, **medium difficulty**, or **high difficulty**. Later in the research, computer algorithms will be used to assign marks along an integer scale such as 1 through 10.

Low difficulty marks will be those that you anticipate will require very little effort to compare (a high quality exemplar is assumed for all of these categories). The mark has high quality and quantity and may also have highly discriminating features. On a 10-point difficulty scale, these would rank approximately 1-3.

Medium difficulty marks are the average marks that make up the bulk of the impressions that you *compare* in casework (not the marks you *see*, which are largely no value). They are not exceptionally clear, nor are they exceptionally distorted. They may have some clear areas and some distorted areas. You may expect that you will put some effort into their comparison, but you are not wishing that you didn't have to compare them at all. On a 10-point difficulty scale, these would rank approximately 4-7.

High difficulty marks are the worst marks you encounter in casework. At the extreme end, they are not of value at all. If they are of value, you wish they weren't. These are marks that you retain for comparison because they meet your agency's minimum suitability criteria, or

if your agency doesn't have a stated threshold, you retain them because you feel they *could* be compared and you would feel guilty if you didn't try, but you know that it will be a very difficult task. They may have low quantity, low clarity, or both. They may be severely distorted. They may lack a target group. They may lack an anchor and will require a "brute force" search. They may lack cues for orientation or anatomical source (i.e. is it a finger or a palm?). On a 10-point difficulty scale, these would rank approximately 8-10.

Once all questions have been answered, you may submit your results (using the "Submit" button, see Figure 8). Once you have clicked on "Submit", it will no longer be possible to modify your analysis or responses and you will be returned to the list of trials page, where you may select your next trial.

6 Practice exercises

Now that you have read the descriptions of the tools available in PiAnoS and the instructions for the trials, you will complete two practice trials to practice using the tools and answering the questions. As you work through these exercises, please try to use every tool (even if you don't need it for these images; you can erase the markings after you try it) and try to apply the instructions and answer the questions as outlined in the user manual, even if some (such as the suitability decisions) feel foreign to you compared to the way you normally complete casework.

If you have any questions about these instructions, the use of the tools, or have technical difficulties, you are free to contact the researchers to clarify or ask for help at any time during the practice or experimental trials. Please do not contact the Principal Investigator, Heidi Eldridge, directly, as this will destroy your confidentiality. If you need to contact Heidi or another member of the research team, please email Cameron Johnson at ctjohnson@rti.org with your query. He will remove all identifying information from your email before forwarding it to the research team to preserve your confidentiality.

When you have completed the two exercises, please email Cameron to notify him that you are finished. Heidi will review your data and get back to you through Cameron within 4 business days to let you know if any instructions appear to have been misinterpreted, and to make sure you don't have any further questions before beginning the experiment. Once you have received feedback and any misunderstandings are clarified, you will be provided with your username and password for the experimental trials.

7 Thank you

Thank you again for your participation! As a small benefit to you for participating, please notice that in the PiAnoS welcome screen, there is a place for you to create your own exercises (Figure 41, Figure 42, and Figure 43). This feature gives you an opportunity to upload images of your own and use the PiAnoS tools available in this version to play with them. It might be useful in exploring tricky images from casework with your colleagues, or just experiencing the joys of marking up lots and lots of tiny features!

Figure 41: The “My personal folder” allows you to upload and store images of your own for use with PiAnoS

Figure 42: This screen allows you to name your exercise and upload the mark image to create your exercise. Please note that TWO images need to be included to create an exercise.

Figure 43: The image library screen. This allows you to select the black box image as your “Print image” since this version of PiAnoS does not allow comparison but still expects a comparison image to be part of the created exercise.